

DEVELOPING INTEREST IN POETRY AMONG ELEMENTARY LEARNERS: MANUAL FOR INTERESTING POETRY INSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to analyze and pinpoint young learners' preferences and interest in reading and in poetry to make it as basis in developing a manual in improving poetry instruction. The quantitative descriptive design using the survey method was used because the study aimed to discover and describe Grade 5 learners' reading and poetry interest and preferences. Data were gathered from 80 pupils in Grade 5 of Felipe G. Calderon Elementary School, Tondo, Manila. A questionnaire survey was administered to the pupil-respondents using the 5-point Likert Scale with the following rating: Very High (5), High (4), Average (3), Low (2), and Very Low (1) to determine their level of interest in reading and in poetry. The findings revealed that Grade 5 pupils have an "Average" level of interest both in reading and poetry. Storybooks are their most preferred reading material while they showed less interest in reading poems though when provided with suitable materials, they would prefer poems about fantasy and those with rhymes. Subsequently, they would want their teachers to teach poetry using silent reading and reading aloud. Ultimately, they lose interest and focus if the material is difficult for them. Therefore, to make young learners become interested in reading, parents and teachers should expose them to reading materials that are suitable, relatable, and within their level of understanding at a very young age to develop intrinsic and permanent desire to read.

Keywords: *interest; poetry; poetry instruction; preferences; reading; young learners*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is an important skill, but it is alarming that people are less interested in it for some reason. Reading is viewed as a highly valued skill in our technology-driven world today (Khairuddin, 2013) but this reality is never realized by many and the number of students who show interest in reading is declining. In this era of technology, people tend to devote most of their time surfing the net, mobile gaming and chatting using social media. In school, reading has been neglected and it has become just a classroom activity. It appears to be low on the list of activities children choose to do in their spare time.

The scenario mentioned is indeed a dilemma since it does not only happen to those who belong to low sections but even in high performing classes. The truth is pupils can read but lack motivation. As observed during English classes, learners show less interest in reading most especially if the lesson being tackled is a poem. Language and Literature teachers are facing problems regarding how to make young learners read poems. The researcher, being a teacher in Grade 5, is alarmed that many pupils are not into reading poems. That is one reason why their skills grow little and their quality as readers also diminishes.

These determinants moved the researchers in pursuing this study. Increasing the pupils' interest in reading poems is the ultimate goal of the researcher, but beforehand, it is important to dig into the root of their noninterest in reading as a whole. There are inhibiting factors which the researcher would like to disclose and give solution to. This study also gives baseline data of the learners' reading habits and preferences in poetry which if considered might revive their interest in reading and eventually motivate them in becoming lifelong readers.

Research Questions

In order to achieve these goals, the following questions were sought to answer:

1. How may the reading habits and preferences of the pupil-participants be determined in terms of:
 - 1.1 length of time spent in reading;
 - 1.2 reading preferences;
 - 1.3 format/ medium used in reading; and
 - 1.4 influences in reading?
2. What is the level of interest of the respondents in the following areas: reading and poetry?
3. How may the interest of respondents in poetry be stimulated through poetry devices, content/ theme, strategies used by the teachers of English?
4. What are the factors that discourage pupil-participants from reading poems?
5. How may a supplementary material (Manual for Poetry Instruction) help in teaching and learning poetry?

METHODOLOGY

The quantitative descriptive design using the survey method was used in this study having questionnaire as the main tool in gathering data, and that it aimed to discover and describe the Grade 5 pupils' reading and poetry interests and their preferences. This was supplemented with interview with teachers of English to strengthen the results of the survey. This study employed quantitative techniques to assess the interest of the pupils in reading and in poetry to be used to develop skills in meaningful poetry analysis.

Quantitatively, a survey questionnaire consisted of (1) reading habits, (2) reading interest, (3) poetry preferences, and (4) interest in reading poems were utilized. The questionnaire also consisted of 10 items to determine the interest and reading as well as interest in poetry using the 5-Point Likert-Scale, namely Very High, High, Average, Low, and Very Low. The items covered the willingness to read, indication of interest in reading, and interest in poetry, effort in making time to read, engagement in reading, and perception on the benefits of reading and of poetry.

Participants

The researcher considered the two highest sections in Grade 5 of Felipe G. Calderon as respondents of this study. Purposeful sampling was used to determine the number of respondents since they are the only sections handled by the researcher; meaning they were picked in terms of accessibility. Therefore, Grade 5 pupils composing of 80 were chosen as respondents.

Materials

Survey questionnaire was used as instrument for this research. Some of the items in the questionnaire particularly in the reading interest section were adapted from Noortyani (2018) but was customized by adding some more suitable items in order to fit the respondents' level and the study itself. It consisted of four sections namely (1) reading habits, (2) reading interest, (3) poetry preferences which also include reasons for disliking poems, and (4) interest in poetry. The second and fourth sections both consisted of 10 items to determine the interest in reading and in poetry which has five options using Likert-Scale, namely Very High (5), High (4), Average (3), Low (2), and Very Low (1). For sections 1 and 3 namely reading habits and poetry preferences, the pupil-respondents were also asked to write their reasons for their responses or choices.

Consecutively, an interview using an open-ended questionnaire was conducted to teachers of English to investigate their views towards poetry and the strategies they use in teaching poetry with their most convenient and permitted time.

Additionally, to identify the respondents' poem preferences, a survey was conducted first through the questionnaire. After the responses were gathered and tallied, the researcher then identified the top 5 most favorite or preferred poems of the respondents with corresponding reasons for choosing, including those which they did not choose. These five poems were used for analysis using the SLAM tool.

Statistical Treatment

The gathered responses were tabulated and arranged into the desired format for use in this study. The respondents' answers from the questionnaire consisting of (1) reading habits, (2) reading interest, (3) poetry preferences, and (4) interest in reading poems were given descriptive analysis using frequency count, percentages, and means. Weighted mean was also used to assess the level of interest of the pupils in reading and in poetry. While the information gathered from the teachers' interview were interpreted qualitatively.

Data Analysis

The survey questionnaire administered to the pupil-respondents also included their reasons for their choices or responses pertaining to their reading habits, poetry preferences, and reasons why they are discouraged to read poems. Moreover, the pupil-respondents were instructed to just choose one option which they considered their most preferred in terms of poetry preferences, reasons why they are discouraged to read poems, and their reading habits. The responses were stipulated as P1 for pupil 1, P2 for pupil 2, P3 for pupil 3 and so forth. Their responses were not altered or improved and were written as is.

RESULTS

This section contains various information and different tables and charts which present the data of the findings of this study.

Part I. Reading interest of the respondents

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the reading interest of the respondents in terms of length of time they spend in reading in a week.

Table 1

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils' Reading Interest In terms of Length of Time Spent in Reading in a Week

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Everyday	5	6.25	4
2	4-6 days	11	13.75	3
3	Less than 3 days	50	62.5	1
4	Never read	14	17.5	2
		N= 80	100%	

It can be inferred from the table that most grade 5 pupils read English materials for at least 3 days and less. It means that even if they belong to the highest sections, reading English materials is not their everyday activity.

Table 2 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of reading interest of the respondents in terms of their reading preferences.

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils' Reading Interest In terms of Reading Preferences

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Story Books	48	60	1
2	Poems	9	11.25	2.5
3	Newspapers	5	6.25	4.5
4	Comics	9	11.25	2.5
5	Magazines	1	1.25	7.5

6	Academic Books	5	6.25	4.5
7	Encyclopedia	2	2.5	6
8	None	1	1.25	7.5
		N=80	TOTAL= 100	

It can be inferred that most grade 5 pupils select story books which according to them are more interesting to read because they contain pictures which they imagine while reading. It is noteworthy that they prefer to read stories like fables and short stories.

Similarly, in the study of Muliati (2017) conducted to fifth semester students, it was revealed that story books belonged to the top three favorites for most students. To reiterate, it was mentioned in the study of Khairuddin (2013) that 45 students liked to read story books while only 17 pupils chose poetry. In the study of Bonto (2015) called *Development of Book Selection Criteria Based on the Reading Interest of Grade 5 Male Students* in Mandaluyong City, Marikina City, and Quezon City, it was revealed that poetry ranked 13th and the least reading material being picked by male students when they have time.

Table 3 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of reading interest of the respondents in terms of their preferred format/ medium used in reading.

Table 3

**Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Pupils' Reading Interest
In terms of format/ medium used in reading**

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Digital/ online	39	48.75	1
2	Printed	36	45	2
3	Read by the teacher	5	6.25	3
		N= 80	TOTAL= 100	

From the table, it can be said that in this generation of computers, the younger generation would prefer to read from the internet because it's more accessible to them. There are more electronic devices at home than books.

Table 4 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of reading interest of the respondents in terms of their influences in reading.

Table 4

**Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils' Reading Interest
In terms of influences in reading**

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Peer/ Friends	8	10	5
2	Parents	24	30	2
3	Teachers	9	11.25	4
4	No one; I just love reading.	10	12.5	3
5	No one; I don't like reading.	29	36.25	1
		N=80	TOTAL=100	

It can be interpreted that grade 5 pupils are not inclined into reading though the respondents belong to higher sections. However, parents are chosen as next to their influencers to read.

Part II. Level of interest of the respondents in reading and in poetry

Table 5 shows the frequency distribution and the weighted mean of level of reading interest of the respondents.

Table 5

Frequency Distribution and Descriptive Measures of the Pupils' Level of Interest In Reading

No.	Items	Frequency					Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	I read even if I am not told to do so.	2	15	44	13	6	3.08	Low
2	I feel excited if I get a reading task.	1	10	20	34	15	3.65	High
3	I choose reading over other activities such as watching TV or playing.	8	29	26	13	4	2.70	Average
4	I do reading activity every day.	4	27	33	12	4	2.81	Average
5	I make special time to read.	8	13	28	20	11	3.16	Average
6	I read after classes are through.	16	25	24	12	3	2.51	Low
7	I read to learn and acquire new things.	0	4	18	32	26	4.00	High
8	I repeat the reading when I find the material difficult to understand.	3	7	16	19	35	3.95	High
9	I believe that reading improves my skills like writing.	4	6	15	27	28	3.86	High
10	Books and other reading materials influence or have impact on my behavior and attitude.	3	6	25	24	22	3.70	High
Weighted Mean							3.34	Average

Overall, the pupils' level of interest in reading is 'Average' with 3.34 weighted mean. This reveals that there is a bit satisfying picture of pupils' reading interest. From the findings, it is evident that they recognized the importance of what reading can provide them, but they can't offer or spend so much time in reading as shown in items 1 and 6.

Table 6 shows frequency distribution and weighted mean of the respondents' level of interest in poetry.

Table 6
Frequency Distribution and Descriptive Measures of the Pupils' Level of Interest In Poetry

No.	Items	Frequency					Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
		1	2	3	4	5		
1	I read poems even if I'm not told to do so.	1 0	2 0	2 6	1 7	7	2.89	Average
2	I feel excited if the lesson is poetry.	1 0	1 3	3 2	1 4	1 1	3.04	Average
3	I choose reading poems over other genres of literature like short stories.	1 6	1 3	2 7	1 7	7	2.83	Average
4	I read poems every day.	2 0	2 4	2 6	7	3	2.36	Low
5	I make special time to read poems.	1 5	2 2	2 0	1 4	9	2.75	Average
6	I read poems after classes are through.	2 3	2 4	2 2	7	4	2.31	Low
7	I find it enjoyable to read poems.	7	1 8	1 9	1 6	2 0	3.30	Average
8	I find it easy to understand poems.	9	1 9	2 7	1 5	1 0	2.98	Average
9	I read poems because it develops my skills like speaking and writing.	1	1 1	1 8	2 8	2 2	3.74	High
10	Reading poems influence or has impact in my life.	4	1 6	1 8	2 0	2 2	3.50	High
Weighted Mean							2.67	Average

It can be inferred that most of them acknowledged the benefits of reading poems. Generally, the pupils' level of interest in reading poems is 'Average' with 2.67 weighted mean. It reveals that pupils' interest in poetry coincides with their interest in reading as a whole. It shows that poem reading is not as interesting to them as shown in items 4 and 6 which are about the effort and time they put into reading poems. But apparently, they recognize the importance of what reading poems can provide them.

The findings reveal that pupils are not into reading poems. Since they recognize the importance of poems, it can be used as motivation for them to give themselves time to read poems even once a day. More exposure should also be done through the teachers' initiative in

using poems in their lessons more often since there are less available books of poems in the library and at home.

Part III. How interest of the respondents in poetry be stimulated

Table 7 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents' choice of poetry devices.

Table 7

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Pupils' Choice of Poetry Devices

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Poems with rhymes	50	62.5	1
2	Poems without rhymes	8	10	3
3	Neither	22	27.5	2
		N=80	100	

It can be inferred that grade 5 pupils are more interested in reading poems if they have rhymes. It means that they show no interest if poems have no rhyming words. For them, rhymes are pleasing to the ears, and they can easily memorize a poem if it contains rhymes.

Table 8 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents preferred content/ theme of poem.

Table 8

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils' Preferred Content/ Theme of Poem

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Nature	17	21.25	3
2	Love	7	8.75	4
3	Humor	0	0	10
4	Friendship	18	22.5	2
5	Special Occasion	6	7.5	5
6	School experiences	3	3.75	7.5
7	Nationalism	2	2.5	9
8	Food	3	3.75	7.5
9	Animal	4	5	6
10	Fantasy	20	25	1
		N=80	TOTAL= 100	

It can be drawn that the top five favorite themes/ content of poems Grade 5 pupils like to read were those about fantasy, friendship, nature, love, and special occasions. This means that Grade 5 pupils prefer these themes/ contents of a poem specially fantasy because young children love to read something they are fascinated with and can relate to.

Table 9 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents' preferred strategy to be used by the teacher in teaching poetry.

Table 9

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils' Preferred Strategies Used by the Teacher in Teaching Poetry

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Read Aloud	21	26.25	1.5
2	Use of Creative Movements	10	12.5	3.5
3	Transforming Poem to Song	5	6.25	6
4	Reader's Theater	0	0	9
5	Silent Reading	21	26.25	1.5
6	Pictures	3	3.75	7
7	Using video/ PowerPoint	10	12.5	3.5
8	Using drawing to illustrate meaning	9	11.25	5
9	None	1	1.25	8
		N=80	TOTAL= 100	

It can be inferred that the pupils' preference when it comes to the strategy used by the teacher in teaching poetry is silent reading because according to the respondents, they want to read a poem silently so they can easily understand what they are reading while for those who selected reading aloud, they said that they want the teacher to read first and model the proper way of reading a poem. Other strategies the pupils wanted to be used by the teacher are use of creative movements/ actions, use of video/ power point, and the use of drawing/ illustration to explain the meaning of a poem.

Table 10 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' reasons for not reading poems.

Table 10

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupils' Reasons for Not Reading Poems

No.	Items	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	It's boring./ No fun	2	2.5	6
2	Too busy/ No time	18	22.5	2
3	No available/ Limited poems	15	18.75	3
4	I can't relate to what I'm reading.	14	17.5	4
5	Words are difficult to understand	24	30	1
6	I just don't like reading.	7	8.75	5
		N-80	TOTAL= 100	

It can be inferred that grade 5 pupils dislike reading poems because they hardly understand the meaning due to the difficult words the poems contain. This means that they easily lose interest if they find the material complex to them.

Interview with Teachers

The questions focused on the teachers' perception in teaching poetry and the strategies or approaches they used in teaching poetry.

When asked about how they find poetry easy or difficult to teach, their answers vary on the level or section of the pupils they teach. They said it's easy if they teach in higher sections because there is no problem with their ability to comprehend, especially if it is a poem. One teacher said that it is quite difficult because most of her pupils belong to lower sections. Only one teacher said it is easy because he enjoys reading and reciting poems.

With regards to the strategy they used, the majority of the teacher-respondents mentioned that they read the poem aloud in order for the pupils to know how the poem is read. Then most of them simply ask their pupils to identify the structure of the poem like rhyming words, stanza, and lines. Haiku is also introduced as early as Grade 3. In Grade 4, the teacher focuses on simply reciting and discussing the poem but not on writing because according to the teacher, they can hardly compose yet. One teacher in Grade 5 said that relatable poems should be introduced to the pupils for them to appreciate the poems. One teacher also focuses on explaining figurative languages because it is what pupils have difficulty with.

One teacher also shared that she used actions when she presented the poem "Trees" by Joyce Kilmer. According to her, when she just read the poem aloud, the pupils seemed not to listen, but when she did actions while reading, the pupils became interested in listening.

In terms of how they feel about teaching poetry, whether they enjoy it or not, all of them said that they enjoy it even if it is hard to teach because of the kind of pupils they handle. For them, one cannot teach something well if he/she doesn't enjoy what he/she is doing. That enjoyment then transfers to the learners aside from the skills acquired. According to them, pupils also enjoy it especially if the topic interests them. This is very important to know because teachers are one of the biggest influences on the pupils.

Finally, when asked about how often they teach poetry in a week, the majority of the teachers teach poetry once a week only, some twice a week. With that note, it can be said that pupils are less exposed but according to them, they just follow the curriculum guide in which less poems are included.

Based on the gathered responses, it can be inferred that pupils are not exposed to poetry that much because it is only being taught once a week or when it is included in the syllabus or curriculum guide.

In conclusion, it can be viewed that teachers play a big role in influencing learners to like and love poetry. Teachers also need to strategize appropriate teaching methods to heighten the students' reception of poetry. A variety of poems should also be provided. In short, it mostly depends on the quality of experiences the teachers provide their pupils in the classroom. It should be noted that there is a link between the teacher and student who display love or distaste towards poetry. It is likely that teachers who show reluctance to teach poetry will, in return, produce students who will also develop distaste for poetry. On the other hand, a teacher who shows enthusiasm towards poetry can influence the learners with the same interest.

Part IV. Manual on Ways to Improve Poetry Instruction

As revealed from the results of this study, the pupils' interest in reading and in poetry both fell under "Average" level. This means that their inclination to reading and to poetry seem

moderate and there is still a little need to push the pupils more to offer time and effort for them to be more interested and have a permanent desire to read. The appreciation of the importance of reading and of poetry is already present in them and that is a very good foundation to ignite such interest.

And so, a manual was developed for teachers of English in the intermediate level to use in their poetry classes that will surely make the learners become interested in reading poems because they would discover that analyzing poems is not difficult using a tool called SLAM. It can be modified considering the level and capacity of the learners. It can also be used for other literary genres, not just poetry. Before the tool could be used, the teacher should have discussed lessons on figurative languages, inferring mood of the characters, inferring tone of a selection, rhymes and rhyme scheme, and other needed skills for this tool to become effective. This tool was modified by the researcher through the inclusion of theories like the metacognitive theory as mentioned in this study.

The tool is of great help to teachers of English on how they could teach poetry in a simple yet meaningful way. As revealed, pupil-respondents are discouraged from reading poems because of their complexity. With that, teaching poems should not be done with complexity but with ease. In that way, pupils would not be afraid and would not feel pressured every time they have a poetry lesson. Through that confidence, they would learn to appreciate poems and eventually, develop in them that intrinsic desire towards poetry. If that is the case, they would also feel the same way about other reading materials or literary genres which are quite easier than poems. As observed and disclosed from this study, young learners become more interested in learning when they understand the lesson or activity. Therefore, as used by the researcher in poem analysis, he preferred the SLAM approach which according to the pupils, analyzing poems became easier and chronological.

It is noteworthy to say that if the interest is already established and permanent, it is easier now to teach more complex reading tasks. To achieve this, teachers should provide reading materials that are relatable, on the level of their grasp, and within their interest. In that way, they will not feel pressured by what they read but instead, there is enjoyment.

DISCUSSION

1. How may the reading interest of the respondents be determined in terms of:

1.1 Length of time spent in reading. Based on the findings, it showed that more pupil-respondents read English reading materials less than three days a week. In contrast, only five pupils liked to read English reading materials every day.

1.2 Reading preferences. Based on the results, it revealed that 48 pupils preferred story books to read compared with other reading materials like poems and comics which were only favored by nine pupils respectively. While five pupils chose to read academic books and newspapers. Besides, only two pupils picked encyclopedia while only one pupil preferred magazines. Finally, there was one pupil who did not prefer any of the reading materials to be read.

1.3 Format/ medium used in reading. From the findings, it was found that 39 pupils preferred to read from the internet (digital/ online) but the gap was not that significant to the number of pupils who chose printed materials as their preferred format/ medium in reading with

36 pupils. Meanwhile there were only five pupils who chose reading materials to be read by the teacher.

1.4 Influences in reading. From the findings, it showed that out of 80 pupils, 29 pupils said that no one influenced them to read because they were not into reading in the first place. While 24 pupils responded that their parents influenced them. On the other hand, ten pupils said that no one influenced them because they just love reading. However, nine pupils chose their teachers as their influencers and eight pupils for peers/ friends.

2. What is the level of interest of the respondents in the following areas?

2.1 Reading. Based on the pupils' responses regarding their level of interest in reading, it was revealed that they have 'Average' level with 3.34 weighted general mean.

2.2 Poetry. With regards to the pupils' level of interest in poetry, it showed that pupils' level of interest in reading poems is 'Average' with 2.67 weighted general mean.

3. How may the interest of respondents in poetry be stimulated through:

3.1 poetry devices. Based on the findings, 50 pupils were interested in reading poems with rhymes while 22 pupils said they do not prefer reading poem whether they have rhymes nor have none. On the other hand, only eight pupils still chose to read poems even without rhymes.

3.2 content. Based on the findings, the top 5 content/ themes of poem mostly preferred by the pupils are: fantasy, friendship, nature, love, and special occasions.

3.3 strategies used by the teachers of English. As revealed, most pupils preferred silent reading and reading aloud as the strategies they want their teachers to teach poetry. They were followed using creative movements and videos/ PowerPoint, using drawing or illustrations to interpret a poem, transforming a poem to a song, and using of pictures.

4. What discourage pupil-respondents to read poems?

Based on the findings, the following reasons were revealed: difficulty of understanding them, no time to read poems because they are busy with other school tasks, no available poems at home and in school, no interest at all in reading poems, and poems are boring to read.

5. How may a supplementary material (Manual for Poetry Instruction) help in teaching and learning poetry?

As gleaned from the results of this study, pupils' level of interest in poetry is 'Average'. It also revealed that they are discouraged to read poems because of the difficulty of understanding them; thus, they lack interest. The researcher believes that interest has a big impact on student's learning and performance. As mentioned in the study of Sarmiento (2016), when interest is high, students read materials that are above their proficiency level. Books that are high in level may be rated as appropriate in difficulty when these are above the students' reading levels. When the interest is low, students often rate books as too hard even when they are below their reading levels. To note, poetry analysis is a highly level activity that requires higher level of thinking skills.

In this present study, the researcher preferred the SLAM tool to ease the task in poem analysis which according to the pupils, analyzing poems became easier and chronological yet

meaningful because it was anchored on the metacognitive strategies like predicting, taking down notes, getting meaning through context clues, using prior knowledge, listening, paraphrasing, and summarizing which are here employed to reach the ultimate goal which is comprehension.

Consequently, a manual is developed for teachers of English in the intermediate level to use in their poetry classes that would surely make the learners become interested in reading poems because they would discover that analyzing poems is not difficult through of course the use of the SLAM tool. It can be modified considering the level and capacity of the learners. It can also be used for other literary genres not just poetry. Before the tool could be used, the teacher should have discussed lessons on figurative languages, inferring mood of the characters, inferring tone of a selection, rhymes and rhyme scheme, and other needed skills for this tool to become effective.

The tool is of great help to teachers of English on how they could teach poetry in a simple yet meaningful way. Teaching it should not be done with complexity but with ease. In that way, pupils would not be afraid and would not feel pressured every time they have a poetry lesson. Through that confidence, they would learn to appreciate poems and eventually, develop in them that intrinsic desire towards poetry. If that is the case, they would also feel the same way towards other reading materials or literary genres which are quite easier than poems. As observed and disclosed from this study, young learners become more interested to learn when they understand the lesson or activity.

It is noteworthy to say that if the interest is already established and permanent, it is easier to teach more complex reading tasks. To achieve this, teachers should provide reading materials that are relatable, on the level of their grasp, and of their interest. In that way, they will not feel pressured by what they read but instead, there is enjoyment.

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered, presented, and interpreted, the following conclusions are drawn by the researcher.

1. The results of this study provided evidence that Grade 5 pupils are not that inclined into reading. Moreover, poems belong to the least reading materials they would pick during their leisure time. One major reason of their hesitance to read poems is the complexity or difficulty of understanding them. On the other hand, they recognize the importance of poems into their studies and lives. It can be assumed that when provided with the right material which they have interest in, comprehension will take place.
2. When pupils are interested in reading, they will perform better on comprehension and read more. Anything of interest to the learners brings satisfaction, and when satisfied, they tend to repeat it. If the interest in reading is already established and permanent, it is easier to teach more complex reading tasks like poem analysis. That could be achieved by considering the

preferences of the learners and providing them with materials that are at their level of understanding without sacrificing the depth of the reading task.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Reading teachers may provide the students with more opportunities for reading. Students should be exposed to books and other reading materials. Mini-libraries inside each classroom should really be imposed and make functional.

2. Teachers should provide a wide selection of easy reading materials which pupils enjoy reading particularly those with pictures. They should, likewise, also offer a variety of reading materials to heighten reading interests and hone reading skills. Teachers should be resourceful in gathering and using materials other than those found in the prescribed textbooks such as inclusion of poem selections in language lesson packages. SLAM tool can be used for a stress-free and chronological comprehension and analysis of poem. Enrichment activities should also be done in the classroom to enhance the lesson as well as generate interest in reading. Teachers should also adjust reading materials to the need and level of the pupils.

3. Pupils' recommendation of a book, story, poem, or any other reading material should also be considered because they are also part of the learning process and besides, it carries more weight than the recommendation of the teachers. Give children the opportunity to share a story or a poem they read to the rest of the class to inspire others.

4.

Teachers should teach poetry more than once a week so pupils will get familiarized and be exposed to this genre in a simplified form that jives with level of the pupils.

5. The school must enrich existing programs like Read-a-Thon and Summer Reading Classes and think and implement other programs to address the needs and preferences of the pupils for better appreciation and learning.

6. Parents not teachers, have the most important role to play in the reading habits of their children as revealed in this study. They may also avail and buy books to be acquired for home use and for their children to read during weekends or long vacations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

There are several ethical considerations that should be taken into account upon the conduct of this study. This includes:

Informed consent: The researcher obtained informed consent from participants and their parents or guardians, explaining the purpose of the study, the nature of their involvement, and any potential risks or benefits.

Anonymity and confidentiality: Participants' identities are kept confidential, and their names are not used in any reports or publications. Additionally, all data are kept secure and confidential.

Respect for participants: The researcher treated participants with respect and dignity and ensure that their rights are protected. This includes ensuring that participants are not coerced or pressured into participating in the study, and that they are free to withdraw at any time.

By addressing these ethical considerations, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted in a responsible and respectful manner, and that the rights and well-being of participants are protected.

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